

CHEMISTRY OF SPIRO-COMPOUNDS. PART I PREPARATION OF CYCLOPENTANE-SPIRO-CYCLOPENTANONE AND CYCLOHEXANE-SPIRO-CYCLOHEPTANONE.

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By the reduction of *cyclopentanone* and *cyclohexanone* with magnesium and aluminium amalgam *dicyclopentane-diol* and *dicyclohexane diol* respectively have been prepared. These diols are accompanied by a certain proportion of *cyclopentylidene-cyclopentanone* and *cyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone*. *Dicyclopentane-diol* on being treated with sulphuric acid undergoes pinacone pinacoline transformation and gives *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexanone*. This on being oxidised yields *cyclopentane-1-carboxy 1-butyric acid*, which yields *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentanone*. *Dicyclohexane-diol* gives a mixture of *cyclohexane-spiro-cycloheptanone* and *dicyclohexene*.

The study of the chemistry of simple spiro-compounds holds out very interesting possibilities. Regarding the nature of these rings, a wealth of information may be available by the determination of the heat of combustion of the hydrocarbons themselves. For the synthesis of these compounds attention was directed towards the preparation of some of the ketones which could then be easily transformed into the required hydrocarbons.

The spiro-ketone, *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexanone* was prepared by Meiser (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2049). It was considered desirable to adopt a similar method for the synthesis of other spiro-compounds. The yield of *dicyclopentane-1:1'-diol* (I) by the method of Meiser, being very meagre, the yield was appreciably increased by the method of Gruber and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2555) and this was further improved by substituting aluminium amalgam for magnesium according to the method of Barnett and Lawrence (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1104). Along with the diol (I), in earlier experiments, with magnesium amalgam, we isolated a large proportion of *cyclopentylidene-cyclopentanone* (Wallach, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2963). In later experiments its quantity was smaller, nevertheless it could be isolated in a fairly appreciable quantity. The ketone was actually a mixture of *cyclopentenylcyclopentanone* (III) and *cyclopentylidenecyclopentanone* (II). An iodometric estimation showed that it consisted of about 25 % of the $\beta\gamma$ - isomeride, the rest being the $\alpha\beta$ - unsaturated compound. The

ketone (II) condensed readily with cyanoacetamide yielding the product (IV).

where $\text{RR}' = \text{C}_4\text{H}_8$ and $\text{R}_1\text{R}_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}$.

The conversion of the diol (I) into the spiro-ketone (V) was almost quantitative, and it could be ranked with the conversion of *cyclopentane-isopropyl-diol* (VI) into 1:1-dimethyl*cyclohexan-2-one* (VII) (Meerwein. *Annalen*, 1910, 376, 152). The spiro-ketone (V) is easily oxidised with nitric acid, giving a mixture of acids from which *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-butyric acid* (VIII) could be isolated in predominantly larger quantity, the other constituent being succinic acid. Thus it is to be inferred that only a small fraction of the compound underwent secondary decomposition. The ketone (V) gives only a monobenzylidene derivative suggesting the presence of one methylene group by the side of the carbonyl group.

The ester derived from (VIII), on being acted upon by sodium ethoxide gives the keto-ester (IX, $\text{X} = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$), which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation produces *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentanone* (IX, $\text{X} = \text{H}$). The

ketone (IX, X = H) gives a monobenzylidene derivative with benzaldehyde

where $\text{R}_3\text{R}_4 = \text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}$.

Dicyclohexane-diol (X) could also be prepared under similar conditions from *cyclohexanone*, being accompanied by quite an appreciable amount of *cyclohexenylcyclohexanone* (XI). The constitution of the ketone (XI) has been established by the formation of a semicarbazone and also by its giving the compound (XII) with cyanoacetamide.

The pinacol-pinacolone transformation with dicyclohexane-diol gives a ketone with a very characteristic camphoraceous odour, accompanied by a large percentage of the unsaturated hydrocarbon $\Delta^{1:1'}$ -dicyclohexene (XIII) (Wallach and Pauly, *Annalen*, 1911, 385, 95).

The ketonic compound should be represented as *cyclohexane spiro-cycloheptanone* (XIV). The ketone has been converted into its semicarbazone and it gives a benzylidene compound with great ease.

The small yield of the ketone (XIV) is rather disheartening. When a sufficient quantity of the material is obtained, it is expected to utilise it for the preparation of *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclohexan-2-one* in a manner analogous to the formation of compound (IX)

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dicyclopentan-1:1'-diol (I).—*cyclopentanone* (90 c.c.) containing mercuric chloride (13.5 g.) was added in a thin stream to boiling benzene (100 c.c.) containing magnesium powder (12 g.), in a 3-litre flask, which was heated on the water-bath. After refluxing on the water-bath for 1 hour, water (30 c.c.) was added and heating continued for 1 hour more. The ben

zene solution was then filtered and the residue extracted with 50 c.c. of boiling benzene. The solvent from the united filtrates was removed under reduced pressure and to the residual oily liquid enough petroleum ether (b. p. 30° - 50°) was added and the mass was cooled with ice when the solid diol (12 g.) separated out fairly completely. From the mother-liquor, the solvent was distilled off and the residue was fractionated under reduced pressure when a further crop of diol (2-3g.) was obtained on its distillation together with an oily liquid which boiled at 108° - $110^{\circ}/5\text{mm}$. The liquid has been identified as *cyclopentylidenecyclopentanone* which yields a semicarbazone, m.p. 224° (cf. Kon and Nutland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3101). The diol crystallised from petroleum (b. p. 70 - 80°) as colourless needles, m.p. 109° . (Found: C, 70.29; H, 10.88. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 70.58; H, 10.58 per cent).

The yield was very much improved by substituting aluminium powder in place of magnesium (cf. Barnett and Lawrence, *loc. cit.*) under the following conditions. *cyclopentanone* (300 g.), aluminium powder (66 g.), mercuric chloride (31 g.) and dry benzene (400 c.c.) were heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. Water (250 c.c.) and some more benzene (450 c.c.) were then added and the heating was continued for 3 hours more. The diol was then worked up as in the previous case giving a yield of 66 g. The by-product, *cyclopentylidenecyclopentanone*, is produced in this case also, though not mentioned by Barnett and Lawrence.

Pinacolin Rearrangement of Dicyclopentane-1:1'-diol: Formation of cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexan-2-one.—The dicyclopentane-diol (20 g.) and sulphuric acid (20%, 150 c.c.) were heated together in a flask fitted with distillation arrangements at 120 - 125° for 2 hours and the distillate was collected. The spiro-ketone was then extracted with ether and the ethereal extract, after washing with sodium carbonate solution and water was dried over sodium sulphate. The ether was then removed and the spiro-ketone collected at $120^{\circ}/45\text{mm}$., yield 16 g. The *semicarbazone* of the ketone was obtained quite readily, m.p. 189 - 90° (cf. Clemo and Ormston, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 352). (Found: C, 63.04; H, 9.15. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_3$ requires C, 63.15; H, 9.09 per cent).

Benzylidene Derivative.—The spiro-ketone (5 g.), benzaldehyde (8 g.), rectified spirit (120 c.c.) and 10% caustic soda solution (30 c.c.) were mixed together and stirred for 3 days. The mixture was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the solvent was then distilled off and the residue freed from benzaldehyde by steam. The residual mass was taken up in ether and the extract, after being washed with 10% caustic soda solution and water was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removing the solvent the residual oil solidified within a short time, yield 5 g. It crystallised from petrol

(b.p. 30-50°) in pale yellow needles, m.p. 75°. (Found : C, 84.7 ; H, 8.3. $C_{17}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.0 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

Oxidation of cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexan-2-one to cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-butyric Acid (VIII).—The spiro-ketone (18 g.) was gradually added from a dropping funnel to a warm mixture of nitric acid (45 c.c.) and water (12 c.c.) heated on the water-bath. When the reaction was over, the flask was heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour more and left overnight. The solution was evaporated on the water-bath with addition of water until nitric acid was completely driven off. The mass was then taken up in ether, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue was kept in a vacuum desiccator for several days when the acid partially solidified and weighed 19 g. The pure acid was obtained from the ester on hydrolysis. It was recrystallised from hydrochloric acid, m.p. 92°; (mixed m.p. with the synthetic acid prepared by Qudrat-i-Khuda and Mukherjee, *vide* second Part, this issue, p. 525).

Ethyl cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-butyrate was prepared from the acid (36 g.) in absolute alcohol (230 c.c.) in the presence of hydrogen chloride as usual. It distilled at 140-142°/6 mm., yield 29 g. (Found: C, 65.79; H, 9.18. $C_{14}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 65.62 ; H, 9.37 per cent). It had $d_4^{32.1}$, 1.017; n_D , 1.449. Found : $[R_L]_D$, 67.59 (calc. 67.96). A small quantity of an ester was obtained as a lower boiling fraction (90-93°/6 mm.) which yielded succinic acid on hydrolysis.

Ethyl cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentan-2-one-3-carboxylate (IX, X=CO₂Et).—To a cold solution of sodium (1.8 g.) in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) the dibasic ester (20 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hours. The alcohol was then distilled off and water poured into the cooled residue. The solution was neutralised with hydrochloric acid, and the separated insoluble oily layer extracted with ether, the ethereal extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed. The keto-ester distilled at 127°/5mm., yield 11 g. (Found: C, 68.20; H, 8.76. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.58 per cent). It had $d_4^{33.8}$, 1.033; n_D , 1.451. Found : $[R_L]_D$, 54.75 (calc. 54.88).

cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentan-2-one (IX, X=H).—The keto-ester (11 g.) was heated on the sand-bath with 10% hydrochloric acid for 4 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the extract washed with sodium carbonate solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. It distilled at 115°/32 mm., yield 7 g. (Found : C, 77.80; H, 10.13. $C_9H_{14}O$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14 per cent). It had $d_4^{32.1}$, 0.9891; n_D , 1.471. Found: $[R_L]_D$, 39.1 (calc. 39.4). The ketone readily gave a semicarbazone,

m.p. 214°. (Found: C, 59.46; H, 9.6. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.01; H, 9.28 per cent)

The *benzylidene derivative*, prepared in the same manner as in the case of *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexan-2-one*, crystallised in pale yellow plates from petroleum ether (b.p. 30-50°), m. p. 64°. (Found: C, 84.5; H, 7.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.9; H, 7.9 per cent).

Dicyclohexane-1:1'-diol (X) was prepared under the same experimental conditions as in the case of compound (I) using magnesium amalgam, yield 15 g. from 98 g. of *cyclohexanone*, while by using aluminium instead, 58 g. of the diol could be obtained from 200 g. of *cyclohexanone*. It crystallised from petrol (b.p. 70-80°), m.p. 130°

Pinacol-pinacolin Transformation of Dicyclohexane-1:1'-diol.—The pure diol (40 g.) and sulphuric acid (50%, 300 c.c.) were warmed on the water-bath for 2 hours when the reaction was complete. The whole thing was chilled, diluted with ice-water and then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium carbonate solution and water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, ether was removed and the product (30 g.) was collected at 110-114°/6mm. It consisted of a mixture of $\Delta^{1:1'}$ -dicyclohexene and *cyclohexane-spiro-cycloheptanone*.

Treatment of the Above Mixture with Semicarbazide Acetate.—Semicarbazide hydrochloride (30 g.) and sodium acetate (40 g.) were dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and to this solution the above mixture (30 g.) was added. To this was added enough methyl alcohol and the solution heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. The alcohol was then distilled off and the solution cooled in ice, when the semicarbazone of *cyclohexane-spiro-cycloheptanone* separated out. The semicarbazone was filtered off and washed with petrol and then with water, the petrol washing being added to the original filtrate. The filtrate was extracted with petrol. From the petroleum extract, the solvent was removed and the residue was again treated with semicarbazide acetate as before to remove the last trace of ketone. After filtration of the semicarbazone, the aqueous portion was again extracted with petrol and the petroleum extract furnished an oily liquid, b.p. 111°/6 mm. The oil was identified as $\Delta^{1:1'}$ -dicyclohexene. (Found: C, 88.47; H, 10.86. $C_{12}H_{18}$ requires C, 88.88; H, 11.11 per cent).

The semicarbazone of *cyclohexane-spiro-cycloheptanone* was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 216-17°, yield 5g. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 9.3. $C_{13}H_{23}ON_3$ requires C, 65.8; H, 9.7 per cent).

Regeneration of cyclohexane-spiro-cycloheptane-2-one from its Semicarbazone.—The thrice crystallised semicarbazone (7 g.) and hydrochloric acid (10%, 70 c.c.) were warmed together on the water-bath for 4 hours,

when an oily layer separated out. The oil was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with sodium carbonate solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was then removed and the ketone was distilled at $120^{\circ}/8$ mm., yield 5g. (Found: C, 79.76; H, 10.9. $C_{12}H_{20}O$ requires C, 80.0; H, 11.1 per cent). It had d_4^{20} , 0.9795; n_D , 1.483. Found $[R_L]_D$, 52.64 (calc. 53.22).

The *Benzylidene derivative* crystallised in pale yellow needles from petrol (b.p. $30-50^{\circ}$), m.p. 123° . (Found: C, 85.2; H, 7.9. $C_{19}H_{22}O$ requires C, 85.7; H, 8.2 per cent).

Condensation of cycloHeptylidene-cycloheptanone with Cyanoacetamide.—To the sodio derivative obtained from cyanoacetamide (4.2 g.), and sodium (1.14 g.) in the minimum quantity of alcohol, the ketone (7.5 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours. The alcohol was then distilled off, water was poured into the residue and the mass acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate was crystallised several times from dilute ethyl alcohol, when a white crystalline substance was obtained, m.p. $215-16^{\circ}$, yield 6 g. (Found: C, 67.15; H, 7.98. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires C, 66.66; H, 7.69 per cent).

Condensation of cycloHexenylcyclohexanone with Cyanoacetamide.—The method was precisely the same as in the condensation of *cyclopentylidene-cyclopentanone* with cyanoacetamide. From 4.5 g. of the ketone, 4 g. of the condensation product were obtained. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. same as given by Sen and Neyogi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 305) who effected the condensation in a different manner. (Found: C, 73.55; H, 8.52. $C_{15}H_{20}ON_2$ requires C, 73.77; H, 8.19 per cent).

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